

STANDARD OPERATION PROCEDURE OF POLYMER DEGRADATION

DELIVERABLE 3.1

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation / Term	Explanation
AF 4	Asymmetrical flow field flow fractionation
Al	Aluminium
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
ATR	Attenuated Total-Reflectance
ATR-FTIR	Attenuated Total-Reflectance - Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy
Ba	Barium
C	Carbon
CA	Contact Angle
DSC	Differential Scanning Calorimetry
EDS	Energy-dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy
EPI	Environmental Product Inc.
ESEM	Environmental Scanning Electron Microscope
FFF	Field Flow Fractionation
FPA	Focal Plane Array
FTIR	Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy
GC	Gas Chromatography
HCl	Hydrochloric acid
HDPE	High-density Polyethylene
KOH	Potassium Hydroxide
LDPE	Low-density Polyethylene
MB	Mater-Bi Novamont
MPs	Microplastics
MS	Mass Spectrometry
NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
NTA	Nanoplastic Tracking Analysis
O	Oxygen
PA	Polyamide
PC	Polycarbonate
PE	Polyethylene
PET	Polyethylene Terephthalate
PLA	Polylactic Acid
PP	Polypropylene

PS	Polystyrene
PVC	Polyvinyl Chloride
Pyr-GC/MS	Pyrolysis Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry
RAIRS	Reflection Absorption Infrared Spectroscopy
RGB	Red, Green and Blue
S	Sulfur
SEC	Size Exclusion Chromatography
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscope
SEM-EDS	Scanning Electron Microscope - Energy-dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
ss-NMR	Solid State Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
TGA	Thermal Gravimetric Analysis
Ti	Titanium
UV	Ultraviolet
WAXD	Wide-Angle X-Ray Diffraction
XPS	X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy
Zn	Zinc

Beneficiaries

#	Short Name	Full legal name
1	UBT	Universität Bayreuth
2	AAU	Aalborg Universitet
3	ENPC	Ecole Nationale des Ponts et Chaussees
4	EVONIK	Evonik Technology & Infrastructure GmbH
5	Fraunhofer	Fraunhofer UMSICHT
6	HHL	HHL Gemeinnützige GmbH
7	KI (NIC)	Kemijski institut (National Institute of Chemistry)
8	NTNU	Norges Teknisk-Naturvitenskapelige Universitet
10	UGOT	Goeteborgs Universitet
11	UiB	Universitetet i Bergen
12	UoP	University of Plymouth
13	VUA	Stichting VU (Vrije University Amsterdam)
14	Univie	University of Vienna

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1 INTRODUCTION

The main component of plastics are polymers – macromolecules, and almost all polymers are organic structures based on carbon, oxygen, nitrogen, sulphur and hydrogen. Organic compounds, regardless of their molecular size, are reactive species that can undergo a range of reactions in the environment during use. Low intensity reactions occur through extended exposure mainly to abiotic environmental factors such as sunlight, the atmosphere, water and mechanical stress. Reactions will alter the chemical composition of the compound. In polymers, chemical changes often lead to breaking of the polymer chain – a structural feature that most profoundly influences polymer properties. The term degradation generally describes a series of unintended reactions that are manifested in gradual changes in polymer properties – ultimately leading to a material that can no longer serve its intended uses.

The range of polymers used in plastics encompasses many different structures that have a profound influence on degradation reactions and mechanisms of a particular polymer. For example, polyolefins have a main chain that is composed only of carbon atoms, whereas the main chain in polyesters will also include oxygen. As a consequence polyolefins are resistant to hydrolysis whereas polyesters are sensitive to it.

Plastics litter in the environment is exposed to environmental factors over long periods so degradation is routinely observed. It is a major factor in the appearance of secondary microplastics (MPs): as larger pieces of plastic litter degrade they lose structural integrity and fragment into small pieces. The process will continue to even smaller particles. The same process occurs with primary MPs albeit from the starting point of physically smaller pieces. Therefore, degradation is critical to the formation and transformations of MPs which will influence the long term fate and impacts of MP pollution. Since many degradation processes occur at surfaces the high relative specific surface area (surface area per mass) of MPs can lead to increased rates of degradation in progressively smaller MP particles.

Degradation reactions alter plastics properties meaning that MPs will have dynamic properties that are not linked solely to physical sizes. For example, degradation will physically and chemically alter the surface of MPs making them more hydrophilic changing surface susceptibility to biofilm formation and potential biodegradation. Changes to the chemistry of particle surfaces may influence adsorption of chemical pollutants it may be exposed to.

Degradation of MPs is a serious challenge for MPs study [1]. Determination of MP particle size distribution can be easily changed during the handling of samples due to brittleness of particles caused by degradation. Spectroscopic determination of material types can be much more uncertain since the material has been chemically altered and will exhibit different spectra than the original structure.

Degradation and its effects is an unavoidable issue in dealing with real plastic pollution and in particular MP pollution [2]. The issue is complicated by the fact that different materials will degrade differently and degradation is dependent on exposure. It is easy to understand that a plastic particle exposed to direct sunlight on the beach or one covered by sediment at the bottom of the ocean will degrade at greatly different rates.

As with organic compounds generally there are two basic reaction types that will occur on polymers under environmental conditions: oxidation and hydrolysis. Mechanisms and reaction rates will differ greatly by material type and conditions.

In the past, polymer degradation has been studied in quite some detail to understand ageing and technological aspects of plastics. The basic chemical mechanisms are therefore relatively well understood. In fact the polymer and plastics industry devoted significant efforts to preventing polymer degradation, either through the selection of suitable processing conditions (drying, processing temperatures, inert atmosphere) and quite extensively through the use of degradation preventing additives such as antioxidants, UV absorbing compounds, fillers, lubricants etc. It is significant that plastics that find their way into the environment as litter also contain these additives since they are generally used in virtually all commercial plastic formulations.

2 PROCEDURES IN ASSESSMENT OF POLYMER DEGRADATION

2.1 Visual inspection

Visual inspection of MPs to assess degradation can be very informative but will be difficult to quantify and will be increasingly difficult to use on particles smaller than 500 µm.

Visual signs of degradation can be put into two main categories:

2.1.1. Discoloration

A change of color will generally occur in particles that have been exposed to natural elements and in particular UV light. Discoloration can generally proceed in the direction of darker colors especially when the original materials are transparent or light colored. Discoloration can also proceed toward lighter colors when the original plastics have more pronounced colors. Discoloration is a surface property caused primarily by UV light that does not penetrate deep into the material. The property is therefore limited to the surface and does not refer to the bulk material. This must be taken into account during a visual examination or when attempting to measure discoloration.

Generally, main polymer types such as PE, PP, PET, PS, PVC, and PC all turn yellow-orange in the course of time as a result of oxidation. The reason behind the discoloration is the accumulation of degraded products of the polymer or other components of the plastic. Common additives like phenolic antioxidants (stabilizer) get oxidized into quinone that imparts yellow color. In PVC photodegradation results in the release of HCl gas that reacts and causes the formation of conjugated unsaturation in the polymer which is observed as yellowing of the material [1].

The limitation of the assessment is that a reference starting color is often difficult to determine. For example, with processing pellets that are often of translucent or beige-to-white color, high levels of discoloration can be observed but a starting point reference is not available. In particles with dimensions in the millimeter range it is possible to cut the particle to expose its core that was not directly exposed to the elements and can be considered as an »internal« reference.

The core of the material can also be exposed, especially in larger debris, when cracking and fragmentation will occur. Cracks and locations of recent fragmentation will reveal the original colour of the material that can be assessed. The advantage of a highly eroded piece of plastic is that discoloration will be more readily visible (due to side-by-side comparison of a recently exposed core and the discolored parts of the same material).

Discoloration is directly visible evidence of exposure of a plastic particle to elements. Observed discoloration can be caused by different reasons among which are pigment discoloration, polymer chemical degradation and sorption of chemical pollutants. Each of these mechanisms will leave a different chemical trace however it is important to understand that in all cases the material reveals a view of its exposure history.

Discoloration can be measured by analyzing the exact colour of the particle in a standard RGB colour scale. The utility of such an analysis as a quantitative measure of degradation has not yet been shown.

2.1.2. Cracking and fragmentation

Physical disintegration of plastics is a direct consequence of chemical degradation that causes a deterioration of mechanical properties. Mechanical stress will enhance the rate of disintegration.

Depending on the material, its exposure to degrading factors and the size of plastic particles physical disintegration can be seen through different indications: a material can develop cracks from the surface towards the interior of the piece. Along these cracks fragments can detach. When only the detached fragments are collected smooth angled surfaces will indicate a recent break. Such surfaces are commonly observed in film fragments and will also indicate mechanical weakness so such fragments are likely to disintegrate upon handling (with a consequence for particle numbers and size distribution!) [2].

Evaluation of physical and mechanical degradation can be assessed through microscopy and mechanical testing:

2.2 Microscopy

Microscopy is a powerful tool to examine physical changes in the material. The range of magnification will depend on the equipment used and can range from low magnifications with a stereo microscope to the highest magnifications achieved with electron microscopy. In the last case the concentration of significant energy that will start melting plastics will be present the strongest limitation for observations.

2.2.1 SEM-EDS

Scanning electron microscope (SEM) provides high-resolution images of the particles by measuring the secondary ions produced by the interaction of electron beams with the plastic sample. SEM coupled with EDS is very useful for chemical and morphological characterization of MPs by measuring diffraction and reflection of emitted radiation from the MP surface. For SEM-EDS, the surface of the sample is scanned by an electron beam that results in the emission of a secondary electron and specific X-ray radiation. Thus, an image of MPs can be created to determine their elemental composition and surface morphology. This technique helps to distinguish MPs with different inorganic elements like aluminum silicates [3]. Fries *et al.* have also reported in their study the presence of inorganic additives; titanium-dioxide nanoparticles with traces of Al, Ti, Ba, S, O, Zn, and C in MP fragments [4].

2.3 Change in Mechanical Properties

Cracking, fragmentation and indicative particle shapes are indications of deteriorating mechanical properties, however they do not offer quantitative evaluation of degradation. It is possible to measure mechanical properties of a material which will give a quantitative measure of changes in the material. This approach appears feasible on items that have a uniform size and shape. Examples would be common objects such as mussel nets, fibres or films.

The variation in crystallinity, crosslinking and chain-scission directly influence the bulk mechanical properties of plastics. In particular, the tensile strength is mostly affected. The measurement of tensile modulus and tensile elongation at break in MPs debris does not always give reliable results. Even if we measure the bulk properties using dog-bone samples we get results average between degraded surface layers of MPs and interior of the plastic material. Except at a higher level of weathering, where the radical species are involved in oxidation within the interior of the thick sample. Carrasco *et al.* [5] reported that FTIR of weathered PE films associates with a decrease in tensile strength. Nonetheless, this may not be true for different plastics or other mechanical properties.

When observed, visual signs of degradation of MP particles, either discoloration, cracking, fragmentation or indicative particle shapes, should be recorded and noted during the particle isolation and characterization process. However further analytical methods will be required to quantify its extent and link it to chemical degradation which is the root cause for the observed changes in properties.

2.4 Chemical changes

Chemical changes are at the core of MP degradation and the direct cause of many different property changes that can be observed at the macro level. To ascertain the extent of degradation it is therefore imperative to employ analytical methodology that will give direct evidence of degradation at the molecular level of polymers or other components of plastics.

2.5 Change in Crystallinity

The degree of crystallinity gets increased by the early stages of weathering. Two factors are responsible for this increase [6]. Firstly, the amorphous polymer is degraded first in weathering. Secondly, chain scission generates short segments of polymers that migrate together and crystallize by 'chemi-crystallization'. The increase in crystallinity can be confirmed by X-ray diffraction or differential scanning calorimetry. However, in the later stage of weathering some of the crystallinity might get reduced [7].

3 ANALYTICAL METHODS IN ASSESSMENT OF POLYMER DEGRADATION

Analytical methods that can provide direct evidence of polymer degradation can be grouped into three main groups:

- Spectroscopy
- Chromatography
- Thermal methods

and of course hyphenated methods that combine methods from either of these three groups.

3.1 Spectroscopy

Spectroscopic analysis is the most commonly used methodology to confirm that MPs are indeed man-made plastics made from synthetic or semi-synthetic polymers. Spectroscopy will enable the identification of the plastic/polymer type. Infrared and Raman vibrational spectroscopy are most suitable and also most commonly used spectroscopy methods. Both will provide a spectrum that is characteristic for a type of polymer and will allow positive identification. In practice a spectrum collected from a MP particle is compared against spectra in a spectral database collection and the best fitting spectra are reported. This process is automatic and embedded in the equipment used. Very accurate matches between measured and database spectra are generally obtained.

Since degradation will alter the chemical structure and vibrational frequencies of molecular structural elements constitute spectra, these changes will start changing the spectrum. Since databases, unless constructed by users for the explicit purpose of evaluating degradation, do not include spectra of degraded polymers the changes in spectra caused by degradation will introduce spectral features not contained within the databases and will result in an increasingly deteriorating fit between measured and reference spectra. A theoretical spectral collection that would include spectra of degraded polymers could easily become prohibitive in size due to the multiplication factors when including different degradation causes and extents. Current databases therefore do not include spectra of degraded polymers.

As a consequence the user analyzing degraded polymers will experience a reduced fit between measured and reference spectra. The comparison of the spectra of pristine and degraded polymer will show the structural change due to degradation. With an increasing extent of degradation, automated matching processes using spectral databases will have difficulty in finding matching reference spectra and will report a lower fit factor between the measured and database spectra, indicating a lower reliability of the characterization. This situation will require the intervention of the operator and a case-by-case analysis of spectral features that can positively confirm the base polymer as well as degradation features. Without this step it is often (reported in the literature) that the characterization was unreliable and the material is reported as unidentified.

To overcome this limitation it is necessary to have the ability to analyze spectral features, and identify differences from spectra of a best matching reference spectrum collected on virgin materials. A simple example is a spectrum of a partially oxidized polyethylene. The measured spectrum will include a peak characteristic for carbonyl (C=O) groups that are not present in virgin materials. This cannot be accommodated by routine analysis using database matching and without a case-by-case analysis of spectra. When a large number of particles are analyzed in an automated process collecting large numbers of spectra as for example in focal plane array (FPA) FTIR microscopy dealing with such deviations is likely not feasible.

To overcome the limitation and still confirm the material characterization it is crucial to identify spectral features that are characteristic to a polymer type and are present in the measured spectra. These are normally dominant. Then deviations in the spectrum should be identified and assigned to functional groups that are known to emerge from degradation. Such a characterization could be confirmed by the availability of virgin and degraded polymer samples however this will rarely be available. The uncertainty of such a «classical» spectral analysis lies in the variability of today's virgin materials: these will include additives, fillers and pigments and can be in form of blends (mixtures) of polymers or co-polymers (containing two or more different monomers). All of these variations will introduce spectral features differing from a spectrum of an undegraded neat single polymer.

In principle degradation will have the effect of introducing new functional groups on the polymer chain or side chains but not leading to chain scission. With more pronounced degradation chain scission will follow leading to shorter polymer chain fragments and the emergence of new (chain) end groups. Each of these changes will be visible in spectra however it should be kept in mind that discernable spectral features emerge only after a concentration (of new structural features) of a few percent is reached. The visibility of a spectral feature caused by degradation can be additionally blurred by overlapping peaks. The combination of all these features makes degradation a relatively difficult feature to identify. Quantification of degradation is even more difficult since a reference plot would need to be available and in particular (FT)IR signals are not reliably quantified.

3.1.1 FTIR

To ensure unambiguous identification of MPs we need spectroscopic or spectrometric methods. Various techniques are utilized to assess the composition, surface morphology and concentration of the MPs. The most widely used technique to measure composition is Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR). The FTIR spectra can be collected in Reflectance, Transmittance and Attenuated Total- Reflectance (ATR) mode. The degradation potential of plastic litter in water is a critical issue for limnologists. In a previous study by Ioakeimidis *et al.*, ATR-FTIR spectroscopy has been utilized to study the degradation of PET bottles, collected from the submarine environment [8]. The expiration date on PET bottles was used to denotative the period that the samples were present in the marine environment as debris. The results revealed that the functional groups of PET remain unaltered for approximately fifteen years. Afterward, few alterations were detected; certain new peaks are observed in the spectra and some even disappear. Hidalgo-Ruiz *et al.* [9] also showed that seventy percent of the visually identified plastic particles are not confirmed by FTIR spectroscopy.

3.1.2 Raman Spectroscopy

Besides FTIR, another technique that is widely used for the detection of MPs is Raman Spectroscopy. It tells us about the bonding within the material and with molecule and networking structure. Both FTIR and Raman Spectroscopy are based on the energy absorption by the functional groups of polymer particles. But the identification of polymers by both the method is susceptible to the addition of additives like plasticizer, UV stabilizer, foaming agent, lubricants etc. which are utilized during the polymer processing and environmental driven changes on the surface of the polymer. Thus soiling, colored plastic, microbial fouling and adsorption of humic acids might interfere with or prevent the identification of the polymer particles [10]. As stated by Van Cauwenberghe *et al.* [11] one of the biggest limitations in Raman spectra is the presence of color interfere in obtaining spectra and sometimes spectra of pigment are obtained rather than the plastics. They observed three different pigments copper phthalocyanine (blue pigment), permanent red (red pigment) and polychloro copper phthalocyanine (green pigment) were measured in Raman spectroscopy, which is widely used in the plastic industry.

3.1.3 NMR

A further step in conventional spectroscopy methods is available through a finer look into the molecular structure using Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectroscopy. The limitation of conventional (solution) NMR spectroscopy is the need for a sample to be dissolved at the molecular level which can be difficult for some polymer types.

With soluble polymers and adequate sample preparation (e.g. separate sampling of degraded surface layers and bulk (particle interior) material) NMR will indicate new functional groups resulting from degradation. The advantage of NMR spectroscopy is that structural feature concentrations can be reliably quantified.

Solid state NMR may be more suitable for MPs study especially with polymers that are difficult to dissolve. In principle ss-NMR will provide the same information as solution NMR however the spectra will give broader signals that can be difficult to assign. Techniques such as high-resolution magic angle spinning are routinely used to improve spectral resolution. With either NMR technique the ability to determine the exact chemical change in the polymer may be complex in the absence of a spectrum for the virgin – undegraded material.

3.2 Chromatography

Chromatography allows separation of molecules based on their chemical structure or on the size - properties which are both affected by polymer degradation. Size exclusion Chromatography (SEC) is of particular use since it is among the few methods that can give a direct insight into the distribution of molar masses (directly linked to chain length). A decisive step in polymer degradation is namely chain scission that can rapidly decrease the polymer chain length that is a key property determining mechanical strength.

The downside of the SEC is that the polymer needs to be in solution. As with NMR this can be a challenge due to poor solubility of some polymers including all crosslinked polymers (duroplastics) as well as the need to limit the analysis only to material on particle surfaces if surface effects are studied. Depending on the detection methods used it is possible to determine relative molar masses (compared to well defined reference polymers) or absolute values for which a reference is not needed.

Other liquid chromatography methods allow separation of polymer molecules depending on the functionality of the polymer that will affect binding of the molecule to a column substrate and therefore the rate of its elution from the column. As functionality will change with degradation this may be a useful method, however it is more demanding than spectroscopic methods and may be less direct for interpretation of results, and ultimately the evaluation of degradation.

3.2.1 Gas Chromatography

Gas chromatography is applied to MPs as part of a Pyrolysis-gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (PY-GC-MS) method. The method is destructive with pyrolysis causing thermal degradation with the subsequent step of gas chromatography separating volatile degradation products and mass spectroscopy serving as a detection method.

Py-GC-MS can be used to assess the chemical composition of MP particles by analyzing their thermal degradation products that exhibit characteristic pyrograms. The method is relative with measured pyrograms compared to reference pyrograms of known virgin-polymer samples. The method has also been used to assess MPs degradation products of several polymers (Dümichen *et al.* [12]).

A particular chromatographic method that functions along different principles is Asymmetrical flow field flow fractionation (AF 4) Field Flow Fractionation (FFF) is a separation technique that applies a perpendicular force on particles in flow. Depending on their characteristics such as density or shape, particles will have different elution times and a separation will occur. This separation is not affected by functionality of the material. AF4 is the most common FFF technique.

The unique advantage of AF4 is that particles smaller than several micrometers can be analyzed by size. The measurement is done on particles without the need for dissolving them. This method is currently not widely applied to MP analysis. In terms of degradation of MPs it is suitable for determination of fragmentation that produces particles in the micrometer and especially in the sub-micrometer range.

3.3 Thermal methods

In thermal analysis of MPs we can apply techniques such as Thermal Gravimetric Analysis (TGA) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) that will determine melting, thermal decomposition and heat flow characteristics of polymers. These properties depend on molecular structure and packing and can indicate a change in crystallinity, functionality and molar mass. These properties are all affected by degradation so changes in them can be used as an indication for polymer degradation.

Of particular interest is the potential change in crystallinity which normally indicates a preferential degradation of either the amorphous or crystalline phase which is an important indication of degradation mechanism and how the material is affected.

Thermal measurements are destructive and it is difficult to separate the measurement of surface and bulk properties.

3.3.1 PY-GC-MS

The most useful application of Pyrolysis-gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (PY-GC-MS) is to analyze polymer type and organic plastic additives simultaneously in a single run without utilizing solvents, thereby avoiding background contamination [13]. The process is done by combustion of the sample and analyzing the thermal degradation products of the polymer, which is specific for each polymer. Due to the combustion of the sample, it is not possible to determine the particle counts. The identification of polymers by studying thermal degraded products acts as a marker. Before the detection of specific mass to charge ratio, the degraded products are separated by GC. In contrast to FTIR and Raman Spectroscopy, PY-GC-MS is a destructive method that does not allow further analysis of the plastic particles. Dekiff *et al.* [14] confirmed that only 47% of a sub-sample of 32 particles that are optically identified as small potential MPs could be assigned to a common polymer type.

4 POLYMER BIODEGRADABILITY

Biodegradation of synthetic or semi-synthetic polymers is an important route to achieving higher sustainability of plastics. It is a useful property with reduced environmental risks and finds valuable applications in various fields like food packaging materials, mulching films etc. Biodegradability may include the action of abiotic factors in the process but is defined by the action biotic factors, mainly microorganisms that use the polymer or its degradation products as nutrients. The polymer is digested leading to environmentally compatible degradation products that are part of natural material cycles. The digestion step is a necessary step in biodegradation.

Biodegradation is however a general concept that needs the definition of the time needed for the process and conditions under which it occurs. It is therefore common to refer to industrial compostability, home compostability, and biodegradation in specific environments such as soil, seawater or freshwater. The exact conditions as well as methods to determine each particular variation of biodegradability are defined in national and international standards and standard procedures.

In the biodegradation process, the polymer ultimately breaks down into carbon dioxide, water and biomass. The process involves three stages: in the first the plastic material is physically fragmented, in the second the polymer structures are degraded to the level of oligomers, monomers and their derivatives, and in the final step these structures are bioassimilated and digested through the action of the enzymatic systems. There are a number of basic processes that take place during biodegradation: biotic degradation, abiotic degradation, the Fenton reaction [15], [16]. Abiotic factors (chemical, mechanical, thermal and light) help to initiate the biodegradation process by weakening the polymer structure [17].

4.1 Biofragmentation

Fragmentation is a physical degradation process in which biodegradable polymers are converted into tiny particles by the combined action of abiotic factors and/or decomposer organisms, microbial communities. The microbial community act on the surface or inside the polymeric material when suitable environmental conditions exist, such as humidity, temperature. Microorganisms may belong to fungi, bacteria, algae and protozoa groups. Consortia that facilitates attachment and matrix formation are commonly referred to as biofilms [18]. The estimation of polymer biodeterioration can be done by evaluating physical erosion, formation of particles, macroscopic modification such as colour change, roughening of the surface, development of microorganism on the surface, measuring weight loss, change in crystallinity and rheological properties [19].

4.2 Molecular biodegradation

Molecular biodegradation is a lytic process in which oligomers, monomers and their derivatives are generated by bond cleavage. Microorganisms cleave polymers by generating free radicals or secrete specific enzymes. Enzymes lower the activation energy of molecules to favour chemical reactions. They are highly specific but require suitable conditions to be effective. Molecular biodegradation occurs through the action of hydrolytic enzymes and oxidative enzymes. It is normally an extracellular process since the substrates are not yet of sizes suitable for crossing the cellular membrane into the cell where digestion (mineralization) takes place. Estimation

of molecular biodegradation can be done by evaluating changes in molecular weight distribution that is a clear indication of polymer chain scission. SEC or viscosity measurements are most suited methods [20].

4.3 Bioassimilation and digestion

In the final stage of biodegradation molecular fragments are transported across the cellular membrane into the cell where they are digested and products used or released. This stage occurs inside the cell and employs the same systems used to digest other (natural) nutrients. As with other nutrients, digestion of molecular fragments from polymers produces energy, and numerous primary and secondary metabolites for the formation of cell structures. The process is vital for cell growth and reproduction. There are three catabolic pathways followed by microorganisms to produce energy and maintain cellular activities, reproduction and structure: aerobic respiration, anaerobic respiration and fermentation. The estimation of bioassimilation is done through the estimation of microbial biomass formation and by standardized respirometry methods. In respirometry, the amount of oxygen consumed and carbon dioxide evolved is measured [21].

Mohee *et al.* assessed the biodegradability of two plastics: Mater-Bi (MB) and Environmental Product Inc. (EPI) under aerobic and anaerobic conditions. In the aerobic test, biodegradability was monitored by determining the mass loss. No variation in the weight for EPI was observed whereas, the weight of MB was decreased by 27.1% in 72 days of composting. In the anaerobic test, biodegradability was monitored by determining the biogas production. The rate of degradation for MB was higher due to a high rate of methane gas production. The EPI plastic did not show biodegradation in anaerobic conditions as well [22].

5 ANALYTICAL METHODS IN ASSESSMENT OF POLYMER BIODEGRADATION

Biodegradation proceeds through several different stages. It is therefore important to select analytical techniques suitable for quantification of the polymer at different stages of degradation. For instance, a little change in mass due to the diffusion of water into the polymer matrix is a reliable method to access the early stage of degradation. The primary techniques used for surface analysis (increase in surface free energy, roughness of surface) of biopolymers are FTIR, contact angle (CA) measurement and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). These techniques give the conformation about the changes occurring at an early stage of degradation. The transition stage of degradation causes chain scission that results in a decrease in the molecular weight of the polymer. The outcomes are a decrease in tensile strength and an increase in porosity of the polymer matrix. During the advanced stage of degradation decrease in polymer weight and the collapse of the polymer matrix is observed. In later stages, the mechanical properties of polymers also decline due to a decrease in crystallinity of polymer [23]. The deviation in crystallinity can be measured by Wide-angle X-ray diffraction (WAXD) and Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) standards techniques are used to test the mechanical properties (tensile, compressive and bending) of the polymeric biomaterials.

Table 3. Examples of analytical techniques used to assess microplastics.

S/N	Sampling	Detection technique	Polymer	Size range	Comments	Ref.
1.	Waste-water treatment plants	ATR-FTIR Micro-FTIR	PE PEST fiber	>20 μm	On average synthetic fibers were higher than MP counts	[24]
2.	Seafood	Pyr-GC/MS Raman	Comparative study	1-5 mm	KOH 10% at 60 °C for 24 h led to digestion of biological tissues with no degradation of polymers except Cellulose Acetate	[25]
3.	Seawater filtrates	Hyper-spectral imaging	Comparative study	>300 μm	Faster techniques that yields false-color near infrared images of the MPs	[26]
4.	Experimental weathering; Oceanic surface water	FTIR	PP LDPE HDPE	>333 μm	Comparative study for the exposure time of oceanic plastic and experimental weathering was more consistent for HDPE	[27]
5.	PS disposable coffee cup lid	Nanoplastic Tracking Analysis (NTA)	PS	224 nm	The degradation of disposable PS coffee cup lid releases nanoparticles of 224 nm after 56 days of exposure	[28]
6.	Pellets and Consumer plastic	Nanoplastic Tracking Analysis (NTA); Coulter Counter techniques.	PET, PLA, PE pellet, PS, PP (film/pellet/sheet)	30 nm - 60 μm	PS and PLA generates the highest particle concentration	[29]
7.	Sand and Sea Water	Artificially thermal decomposition; GC/MS	Styrene (monomer/dimer/trimer)	-	Styrene monomer/dimer/trimer has higher conc. In sand than seawater	[30]
8.	Prepared PET film ($M_w \sim 70.000$)	FTIR-RAIRS	PET film	100 nm	Hydrolytic degradation in alkaline solution is a random process while in water it occurs preferentially at terminal ester sites	[31]
9.	Sediments	PY-GC-MS; SEM – Energy-dispersive X-ray	PE, PP, PS, PA, chlorinated PE, chloro-sulfonated	-	Have advantage to analyze polymer and additives (plasticizer, antioxidants etc.) in one run without using solvents	[4]

		Spectroscopy (SEM-EDS)	PE, phthalates			
10.	Sediments of lagoon	μFTIR; Environmental SEM - energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (ESEM-EDS)	PE, PP (in abundance)	30 – 500 μm	Potential source to enter the food web	[32]

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